

ARGO: Autonomous inspection of RollinG stOcks

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Abstract—In the field of the condition based maintenance, the ARGO robot is a railway inspection platform designed to move under the trains, both on standard and elevated tracks, in order to collect high quality visual data of critical components. Train inspection is usually performed by human personnel in dedicated facilities, equipped with inspection pits. The peculiar ability of ARGO to operate on conventional railway tracks extends the inspection capabilities outside the conventional maintenance plants, with the potential to significantly change costs, time and frequency of the inspections. The proposed system can both perform autonomous inspection or be remotely teleoperated by using the operator control interface, including software functionalities to store and generate the final inspection report. The system has been already evaluated in two different train inspection facilities, and also operated directly by on-field inspection personnel.

Index Terms—Condition based maintenance, inspection, robotics, rolling stocks

I. INTRODUCTION

Ordinary maintenance processes represent a critical and fundamental aspect to achieve safety and efficiency in the rail transportation sector. Condition Based Maintenance (CBM) is a growing approach to improve both safety and reliability as well as decreasing cost of operation [1]. The identification of the effective parameters to define vehicle's condition and their measurable effects [2], can be used together with cost prediction models for planning the maintenance strategy that minimizes the total cost of maintenance process [3]. Existing robotic systems in the railway industry are mainly dedicated to the inspection of the infrastructure. Loccioni company produces Felix [4], developed in partnership with Rete Ferroviaria Italiana (RFI), a mobile robot for inspection of rail exchanges and intersections. Artificial vision techniques for automatic inspection of the railway line have also been proposed: systems based on a line of cameras [5] and on laser scanners [6] have been developed and experimentally tested on a railway vehicle for detection of defects in ties and fasteners, and in [7] for inspection of the clearing gauge on railway vehicles. Fixed inspection systems are proposed for inspection of railway vehicles, in particular for wheel parts and dimensions [8]. The manuscript presents the ARGO (Autonomous inspection of RollinG stOcks) robot [9], a robotic platform with specific design solutions, enabling an on-condition maintenance paradigm of the rolling stocks. ARGO is able to perform inspection of the train underbody on conventional railway tracks, hence extending the inspection capabilities outside the conventional facilities equipped with inspection pits. ARGO was born from a partnership between

Fig. 1: The ARGO robot tested in a railway maintenance facility

Trenitalia Spa, Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA) and Next Generation Robotics srl.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE VEHICLE

A distinctive feature of the ARGO system is the capability to move beneath the inspected train, using the thin gap between the internal sides of the rails and the ground. ARGO robot is shown in Figure 1 evidencing the peculiar flat shape with side active wheels. It is battery powered and all its parts are at least IP65 protected. The overall dimensions allow ARGO to move under all the rolling stocks designed according to the loading gauge standard UIC 505-1.

A. Motion & Setup System

ARGO can move both on standard and elevated tracks, thanks to its innovative patented motion system (patent WO2017IB56006), shown in Figure 2a-A and Figure 2a-B. Further, each motion unit slides on a linear guide on the robot chassis, so that they can be pulled back to reduce the robot encumbrance. This is needed to permit the robot to be inserted between the rails or removed from them. The linear motion is generated by a power screw linear motor, that moves two motion units simultaneously – front/back left and front/back right, with respect to robot motion direction Figure 2a-A. In each of the motion unit, the vertical idle wheel and the horizontal traction wheel are connected by a linear spring; when the linear motor pushes out the two vertical idle wheels, the horizontal traction wheels are pushed against the rail, generating a suitable preload to ensure that the proper thrust force can be generated and to make robot motion self-centering (Patent application n. 102022000001133).

(a) A) CAD Rendering of the automatic setup mechanisms of ARGO. B) Patented passive and active wheel systems to perform both traction and support on the inner part of the rail. C) Extended retractable arm shaped like the rail head. D) CAD rendering of the ARGO robot with all the retractable arms extended.

(b) Vision system detail

(c) Operator Interface

In order to facilitate insertion of the robot in the operating workspace between the rail sides, an embedded retractable mechanism has been developed (patent application n. 102022000001136). It is composed of two couples of retractable support arms – four-bar linkages, each actuated by a hybrid stepper motor, with ends shaped like the rail head (Figure 2a-C and Figure 2a-D). During normal operation the arms are retracted into the robot chassis. The engage-disengage procedure is fully autonomous and can be easily performed by an operator step by step using the remote-control interface.

B. Vision system & remote control interface

The vision system consists of two upwards-facing wide-angle HD cameras and a white LED light in between them (Figure 2b). Sensors are mounted on an actuated linear guide. The designed 2 cameras system allows to inspect the most lateral parts of the undercarriage. The combination of field of view – 102.8° – and linear motion allow to inspect the whole undercarriage from a “horizontal perspective”. The minimum distance from camera to train is 10 cm. The selected resolution (3,15 MP) and camera sensor ($3.45 \mu\text{m}$), in combination with the fixed-focal (3.5 mm) lens, ensures a precision of 1 mm at 1 meter distance.

ARGO can be remotely controlled through a web application GUI (Figure 2c). The robot can be moved using the stick for high speed motion or the vertical slider for low speed motion placed in the right control panel. Moreover, the two upper rectangular panels contain streaming from the robot cameras. From the GUI it is possible to move the vision system select which camera to stream, enable/disable the streaming, and take high quality pictures or videos and store them.

III. ON FIELD TESTING & CONCLUSIONS

At the current date the ARGO system has been successfully tested in two different Trenitalia’s maintenance facilities, as-

sessing its main functionality to move under an inspected train and to acquire detailed images of specific parts of interest. Although the main components are clearly visible (i.e. brake pads, pneumatic and electrical connections, integrity of the main wheel axis, etc...), improvements can be performed to reduce the presence of certain blind spots. Further on-field experimentation with extended image acquisition will provide the required data to train the system in identification of anomalies and estimation of incoming failures.

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